

A Comparative Study of Early Versus Delayed Laparoscopic Cholecystectomy in Acute Cholecystitis and its Associated Complications

Kumar Gaurab¹, Kumar Ratnesh², Himanshu Kumar³, Swapnil⁴

¹Junior Resident, Department of General Surgery JLNMC Bhagalpur

²Associate Prof. Department of General Surgery JLNMC Bhagalpur

³Senior Resident, Department of General Surgery JLNMC Bhagalpur

⁴Junior Resident, Department of General Surgery JLNMC Bhagalpur

Received: 20-04-2023 / Revised: 17-05-2023 / Accepted: 10-06-2023

Corresponding author: Dr Swapnil

Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:

Background and Objectives: Acute cholecystitis is a common surgical problem and was usually treated with conservative management followed by a delayed laparoscopic cholecystectomy after an interval of 6 to 8 weeks. Our aim was to compare the efficacy of immediate laparoscopic cholecystectomy (ELC) with delayed laparoscopic cholecystectomy (LLC) in patients of acute cholecystitis, and also to assess the complications between the two.

Materials and Methods: This is prospective Study randomized controlled trial in JLNMC and Hospital Bhagalpur. Study duration of Two years. that was conducted on 50 consecutive patients diagnosed to have acute cholecystitis. 25 patients underwent immediate laparoscopic cholecystectomy within 24-72 hours of admission and 25 patients underwent a delayed laparoscopic cholecystectomy after 6-8 weeks of the initial episode.

Conclusion: Early laparoscopic surgery had similar intraoperative and postoperative complications compared to delayed surgery in acute cholecystitis but was associated with a shorter surgery and lesser stay in hospital.

Keywords: Early laparoscopic cholecystectomy, Delayed laparoscopic cholecystectomy, Late laparoscopic cholecystectomy, acute cholecystitis

This is an Open Access article that uses a funding model which does not charge readers or their institutions for access and distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0>) and the Budapest Open Access Initiative (<http://www.budapestopenaccessinitiative.org/read>), which permit unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided original work is properly credited.

Introduction

Acute cholecystitis is a common general surgical emergency scene in various setting from district hospital to specialized tertiary level institutions. [1] Acute cholecystitis is due to gallstones in up to 90% of patients the reported prevalence of gallstones is up to 10% in adult Eastern population and upto 15% in adult Western population. It is estimated that 20 to 40% of individuals with gallstones will develop associated symptoms and 12% will

develop after cholecystitis. [2] First performed in 1985 by Dr. Erich Muhe. Laparoscopic cholecystectomy has now replaced open cholecystectomy as a first choice of treatment for gallstones and information of the gallbladder unless contraindications are found with the laparoscopic approach. With the development in laparoscopic skills and equipment, laparoscopic cholecystectomy has been reported to have significantly

lower complication rates than open cholecystectomy. [3] Now-a-days, laparoscopic cholecystectomy for acute cholecystitis are mainly performed after the acute episode occurs while conservative therapy, usually antibiotics, and delayed laparoscopic cholecystectomy are still common in many centers. [3] Laparoscopic cholecystectomy is currently the gold standard treatment. [4] Many prospective randomized studies demonstrated that early cholecystectomy within 7 days of the onset of symptoms was the preferred strategy to manage the acutely inflamed gallbladder, because of shorter hospital stay and reduced potential risk of late complications such as gangrenous or emphysematous cholecystitis, without an increase of postoperative morbidity and mortality. [5] However, the timing of laparoscopic cholecystectomy still remains controversial regarding the inflammation, edema, and adhesions during the acute course of the disease. [3]

Objectives

To assess the benefits of early laparoscopic cholecystectomy compared with delayed laparoscopic cholecystectomy in patients with acute cholecystitis.

To assess the complications associated with early laparoscopic cholecystectomy and delayed laparoscopic cholecystectomy in patients with acute cholecystitis.

Material and Methods

This is prospective Study randomized controlled trial in JLNMC BHAGALPUR. that was conducted on 50 consecutive patients diagnosed to have acute cholecystitis. 25 patients underwent immediate laparoscopic cholecystectomy within 24-72 hours of admission and 25 patients underwent a delayed laparoscopic cholecystectomy after 6- 8 weeks of the initial episode. All patients presenting with acute cholecystitis to Jawaharlal Nehru Medical College and Hospital

Bhagalpur Bihar. Study duration of Two years.

Inclusion criteria

All adults, between the ages 25 to 60 years, were chosen for the study who presented with features of acute cholecystitis, and were then diagnosed with acute cholecystitis based on clinical and relevant investigations.

Acute upper abdominal pain with tenderness under the right costal margin; fever more than 37.5 C. Leukocytosis.

Ultrasonographic evidence (thickened gallbladder wall, edematous wall, and presence of gallstones, ultrasonographic Murphy's sign, and pericholecystic fluid collection).

ERCP optional.

Exclusion criteria

Adults also diagnosed to have the following were excluded:

Acute pancreatitis,

Cholangitis

Choledocholithiasis

This was a randomized control study and the randomization was done by odd-even method.

The sample size of the study was 50 patients.

Patients fulfilling the selection criteria were invited to participate in the study and informed consent was taken.

Patients were clinically examined and following investigations are done:

CBC, RFT, LFT, GRBS, SERUM ELECTROLYTES, SEROLOGY, URINE ROUTINE AND MICROSCOPY. USG ABDOMEN ,CHEST X-RAY, ERCP optional

All selected patients were randomized into two groups – one group underwent early laparoscopic cholecystectomy (ELC) and

the second group underwent delayed or late laparoscopic cholecystectomy (LLC).

The early operation group was operated on within 24 -72 hours of admission(25 patients), whereas the late operation group were started on conservative treatment and were discharged after a complete

relief of symptoms and were called for laparoscopic cholecystectomy after 6 or 8 weeks, when the acute episode had subsided (25 patients).

All patients were followed up till postoperative discharge of the patient.

Results

Table 1: Distribution of subjects according to sex between 2 groups (ELC and LLC)

SEX	SURGERY		Total	P value
	ELC	LLC		
Female	12	12	24	1.00
	48.0%	48.0%	48.0%	
Male	13	13	26	
	52.0%	52.0%	52.0%	
Total	25	25	50	
	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	

48% of the subjects were female and 52% of them were male. Male and female had equal distribution in both types of surgery .There was no statistical significant difference found between distribution of subjects according to sex between 2 groups (ELC and LLC).

Table 2: Comparison of Mean Age between 2 groups (ELC and LLC)

	SURGERY	Mean	Std. Deviation	P value
Age (in years)	ELC	40.16	10.148	0.227
	LLC	36.92	8.490	

Mean age in ELC was 40.16yrs±10.14yrs and Mean age in LLC was36.92yrs±8.49yrs. There was no statistical significant difference found between the mean ages between 2 groups (ELC and LLC).

Table 3a: Distribution of subjects according to vomiting between2 groups (ELC and LLC)

Vomiting	SURGERY		Total	P value
	ELC	LLC		
NO	13	18	31	0.260
	52.0%	72.0%	62.0%	
YES	12	7	19	
	48.0%	28.0%	38.0%	
Total	25	25	50	
	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	

12 patients (48%) in ELC group and 7 patients (28%) in LLC group presentedwith complaints of vomiting. There was no statistical significant difference found between vomiting between2 groups (ELC and LLC).

Table 3b: Distribution of subjects according to guarding between 2 groups (ELC and LLC)

Guarding	SURGERY		Total	P value
	ELC	LLC		
NO	23	23	46	1.000
	92.0%	92.0%	92.0%	
YES	2	2	4	
	8.0%	8.0%	8.0%	
Total	25	25	50	
	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	

On examination 2 patients (8%) in ELC group and 2 patients (8%) in LLC group had guarding. There was no statistical significant difference found between guarding between 2 groups (ELC and LLC).

Table 4: Distribution of subjects according to pericystic fluid collection between 2 groups (ELC and LLC)

Pericystic Fluid Collection	SURGERY		Total	P value
	ELC	LLC		
NO	13	8	21	0.176
	52.0%	32.0%	42.0%	
YES	12	17	29	
	48.0%	68.0%	58.0%	
Total	25	25	50	
	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	

12(48%) patients in ELC and 17(68%) patients in LLC were found to have pericystic fluid collection. There was no statistical significant difference found between pericystic fluid collection between 2 groups (ELC and LLC).

Table 5: Comparison of mean duration of surgery between the 2 groups (ELC and LLC)

	Surgery	Mean	Std. Deviation	P value
Duration of surgery (in mins)	ELC	76.16	23.387	<0.001
	LLC	116.48	23.141	

Mean duration of surgery was more in LLC when compared with ELC. There was a statistical significant difference found between duration of surgery and the 2 groups

Table 6: Comparison of mean hospital stay between the 2 groups (ELC and LLC)

	SURGERY	Mean	Std. Deviation	P value
HOSPITAL STAY (in days)	ELC	3.84	2.267	.039
	LLC	6.48	5.774	

Mean hospital stay was more in LLC when compared with ELC (6.48 days vs 3.84 days). There was a statistical significant difference found between

hospital stay and type of surgery

Discussion

Acute cholecystitis develops in up to 10% of patients with symptomatic gall stone

disease. In 90 -95% of cases, acute cholecystitis is related to gall stone disease and is caused by complete obstruction of the cystic duct. At the time of introduction of laparoscopic cholecystectomy, acute cholecystitis was a relative contraindication, but with increased experience, laparoscopic cholecystectomy has become the gold standard method to treat the condition.

Till recently, a patient with acute cholecystitis would be treated non-operatively and would be advised an interval cholecystectomy – which was usually planned after 6 to 8 weeks. Over years, many randomized controlled trials have demonstrated no difference in morbidity among patients undergoing early versus delayed surgery. In fact, early cholecystectomy reduced overall hospital stay and costs. Early cholecystectomy also decreases the risks of failed conservative management and recurrent bouts of acute cholecystitis in the waiting period. In our study, the mean age of patients undergoing early laparoscopic cholecystectomy was $40.16\text{yrs} \pm 10.14\text{yrs}$ and the mean age in late laparoscopic cholecystectomy group was a statistically comparable $36.92\text{yrs} \pm 8.49\text{yrs}$. 13 female and 12 male patients underwent early cholecystectomy and 13 female and 12 male patients underwent late laparoscopic cholecystectomy respectively. Totally, 48% of subjects were male and 52% of them were female. In a study by Ann Y. Lee et al [6], the mean age of patients in ELC age group was $44 \pm 16\text{yrs}$ while in LLC group was $42 \pm 14\text{yrs}$ and was found to be statistically insignificant as well. A study by Alper Bilal Ozkerdes (2014) [7] showed that both groups revealed similar physical examination findings: all patients had tenderness and defence in the abdominal area (this term means tensing the muscles in the abdominal area, a clinical finding that may present when the internal organs are inflamed in some manner) and 90% had Murphy sign, and 13.3% in the early and 26.7% in the late

laparoscopic cholecystectomy groups had rebound tenderness. Blood count and liver function results were not different between groups. Another study conducted by Abdulmohsen A et al (2008) [8] showed that there were 2 conversions (2.4%) in ELC and 8 in LLC (7%) ($P=0.3$). Obscure anatomy at Calot's triangle was the sole reason for conversion in group 1. A study by Christos Skouras (2012) [9] showed no significant difference was demonstrated in the morbidity, but the DLC group had a larger number of complications (13% in the ELC group versus 29% in the DLC group, $P=0.07$). One of the DLC patients that underwent an urgent interval procedure suffered a common bile duct injury, which was managed with a hepaticojejunostomy. Guruswamy et al (2013) [10] performed a meta-analysis of 5 randomized controlled trials; the RCTs of Lo et al, Lai et al, Johansson et al and Kolla et al were included, as well as the RCT of Dávila et al. A study conducted by Zhu B et al (2012) [11] showed that patients undergoing ELC experienced a significantly shorter operating time (44.1 ± 5.32 vs. 66.4 ± 3.05 min, $p < 0.01$). There was no significant difference regarding wound infection rates [$1/34$ (2.94 %) vs. $2/99$ (2.02 %), $p > 0.05$] or postoperative hospital stay (6.50 ± 1.31 vs. 6.67 ± 0.73 , $p > 0.05$) between groups. A retrospective analysis by Minutolo V (2014) [12] included 91 patients, 52 female and 39 male, with a mean age of 55. Early surgery was performed in 32 cases and delayed surgery in 59 cases. The two groups were comparable for demographics data and severity of disease on admission. Uchiyama K et al 2004 [13] : A retrospective analysis of 73 patients with acute cholecystolithiasis who were treated by either early laparoscopic cholecystectomy within 72 hours after initial onset or initial conservative treatment followed by delayed laparoscopic cholecystectomy 4 days later. A retrospective cohort study by

Sánchez-Carrasco M et al (2016) [14] included 1043 patients, with a group of 531 EC cases and a group of 512 DC patients. The following parameters were recorded: (1) postoperative hospital morbidity, (2) hospital mortality, (3) days of hospital stay, (4) readmissions, (5) admission to the Intensive Care Unit (ICU), (6) type of surgery, (7) operating time, and (8) reoperations.

Conclusion

DLC is associated with a longer total hospital stay but equivalent morbidity as compared to ELC for patients presenting with acute cholecystitis. ELC would appear to be the treatment of choice for patients presenting with ELC.

References

1. Gananadha S, Fergusson J. Moderate acute cholecystitis: To cut now or to cut later. *J Gastroenterol Hepatol*. 2009;24(12):1806-1807.
2. Menahem B, Mulliri A, Fohlen A, Guittet L, Alves A, Lubrano J. Delayed laparoscopic cholecystectomy increases the total hospital stay compared to an early laparoscopic cholecystectomy after acute cholecystitis: an updated meta-analysis of randomized controlled trials. *HPB*. 2015;17(10):857-862.
3. Zhou M, Gu X, Xiang J, Chen Z. Comparison of clinical safety and outcomes of early versus delayed laparoscopic cholecystectomy for acute cholecystitis: A meta-analysis. *The Scientific World Journal*. 2014; 2014:1-8.
4. Ozkardes AB, Toka M, Dumlu EG, Bozkurt B et al. Early versus delayed laparoscopic cholecystectomy for acute cholecystitis: Prospective, randomized Study. *J Int Surg* 2014; 99:55-61.
5. Minutolo, Liccardello, Arena et al. Laparoscopic cholecystectomy in the treatment of acute cholecystitis: Comparison of outcomes and cause between early and delayed cholecystectomy. *J European Review For Medical and Pharmacological Sciences* 2014;18 Suppl 2) :40-46.
6. Ann Y Lee, Joseph J. Carter, Mark S. Hochberg, et al. The timing of surgery for cholecystitis: a review of 202 consecutive patients at a large municipal hospital. *Am J Surg*. 2008 Apr;195(4):467-70.
7. Alper Bilal Özkardeş, Mehmet Tokaç, Ersin Gürkan Dumlu, Birkan Bozkurt, Ahmet Burak Çiftçi, Fahri Yetişir, Mehmet Kılıç. Early versus delayed laparoscopic cholecystectomy for acute cholecystitis: A prospective, randomized study. *Int Surg*. 2014 Jan-Feb; 99(1):56–61.
8. Abdul Mohsen A. Al-Mulhim. Timing of Early Laparoscopic Cholecystectomy for Acute Cholecystitis. *JLS*. 2008 Jul-Sep; 12(3):282–287.
9. Skouras C, Jarral O, Deshpande R, Zografos G, Habib N, Zacharakis E *Int J Surg*. Is early laparoscopic cholecystectomy for acute cholecystitis preferable to delayed surgery?: Best evidence topic (BET). 2012;10(5):250-8.
10. Gurusamy K. Early laparoscopic cholecystectomy appears better than delayed laparoscopic cholecystectomy for patients with acute cholecystitis. *Evidence-Based Medicine*. 2015; 21(1): 28-28.
11. Zhu B, Zhang Z, Wang Y, Gong K, Lu Y, Zhang N. Comparison of Laparoscopic Cholecystectomy for Acute Cholecystitis within and Beyond 72 h of Symptom Onset During Emergency Admissions. *World Journal of Surgery*. 2012;36 (11):2654-2658.
12. Minutolo V, Liccardello A, Arena M, Nicosia A, Di Stefano B, Cali G, Arena G. Laparoscopic cholecystectomy in the treatment of acute cholecystitis: comparison of

- outcomes and costs between early and delayed cholecystectomy. *Eur Rev Med Pharmacol Sci.* 2014 Dec;18(2 Suppl):40-6.
13. Uchiyama K, Onishi H, Tani M, Kinoshita H, Ueno M, Yamaue H. Timing of laparoscopic cholecystectomy for acute cholecystitis with cholecystolithiasis. *Hepatology.* 2004 Mar-Apr;51(56):346-8.
14. Sanchez-Carrasco M, Rodriguez-Sanjuan J, Martin-Acebes F, Llorca-Diaz F, Gomez-Fleitas M, Zambrano Munoz R et al. Evaluation of early cholecystectomy versus delayed cholecystectomy in the treatment of acute cholecystitis. *HPB Surgery* 2016;2016:1-8.